

CREATIVE LEGACY OF ALISHER NAVAI

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5918202>

Annotation

The pen of the brilliant Uzbek poet, thinker and statesman Alisher Navai owns more than thirty artistic, scientific and journalistic works. Like many other poets of that time, Alisher Navai wrote his works in two languages. However, the main works of the outstanding poet were written in the Turkic (Old Uzbek) language, and this raised the Uzbek classical literature to an unprecedented height.

Key words: *thinker and statesman, classical literature, creative legacy, literary heritage, tatabbu, rediff*

It was Alisher Navai who became the founder of not only Uzbek literature, but also the modern Uzbek literary language. The creative legacy of Alisher Navai is not a collection of individual bright and talented works, but a holistic artistic picture of the world, the life of a great master. Of course, thoughts and worldview, attitude to life and society are the views and ideas not only of Navai himself, but also of people of that distant era, conveyed through the prism of the author's perception. That is why the analysis of the work of the great Uzbek poet is extremely important and interesting. The main part of Alisher Navai's literary heritage is his subtle and amazing lyrics. Alisher Navai began his work with lyrics and continued to write lyrical ghazals until his death. This poetic genre was not abandoned by the poet even when he created his dastans and prose works. Navai's poems, which were included in his early divan, were written before 1465, mainly in Mashhad and Herat. The historical environment in which the young Navai lived and worked not only determined the formation of his worldview and poetic skill, but also to a certain extent was reflected in his early lyrics. It is also appropriate to note here the poetic traditions of the Muslim East, which played an important role in the development of the poet's early lyrics. Particularly strong influence on Alisher Navai was exerted by outstanding predecessors and contemporaries, first of all Khosrov Dekhlevi, Hafiz Shirazi and Abdurakhman Jami, and Atoi, Sakkaki and Lutfi, who worked in the Uzbek language. Navai valued the latter especially highly and considered him his teacher. Perhaps that is why

many of the poems of the young Navai, distinguished by the ease of style and a kind of creative manner, strongly resemble the gazelles of Lutfi. Navai's attitude to the literary tradition was manifested in various forms in his early poems. So, Navai turned to the tatabbu method in the initial period of his work and mainly used it in his Persian poems. Tatabbu is a method of creative competition between two poets, one of whom, under the impression of the other's work, while retaining some poetic features (rhyme, redirect, rhythm) and using them, creates his own work that rivals the original, and sometimes, as in the case of Navai, and surpasses it. For example, in the collection "Divani Fani" 349 gazelles are written in the form of tatabbu on the works of famous Persian-Tajik poets: 23 gazelles - on the gazelle of Saadi, 243 - on the gazelle of Hafiz, 36 - on the gazelle of Khosrov Dekhlevi and 47 - on the gazelle of Abdurakhman Jami. Along with tatabbu, the young Navai also uses another method: from the poems of his predecessors, he takes a rhyme or a rediff, figurative expressions or structure and on this basis creates his original poem. Such a poetic device was extremely popular in the East. The lyrical tradition of eastern poetry also plays a great role in shaping the themes of Alisher Navai's early lyrics. So, love was and in many ways remains the main theme of eastern poetry. And it is not by chance that the genre of the gazelle itself - the most common poetic form of that time - is characterized precisely by the fact that it, as a rule, expresses the suffering of the unrequited love of the hero, the lover's complaints about fate, about evil fate, the unique female beauty is sung. The basis of the richest lyrical heritage of Alisher Navai is his famous «Treasury of thoughts», consisting of four sofas: «Miracles of childhood», «Rarity of youth», «Curiosities of middle age» and «Useful tips of old age». The total volume of the collection amounted to more than forty-five thousand lines. Alisher Navai himself described his collection as follows: «Although the time for which the sun illuminating the world makes one circle in the sky is called a year, a year consists of four times, and each such period has a special name. Just as the results of the rotation of the sun in the sky are the riches of the bowels and seas, and vegetation, and the animal world, in the same way, evidence and examples can be found from all these results. In contrast to the four seasons, four sofas appeared, each of which received an appropriate name. Therefore, the first sofa, which is decorated with wonderful roses of the buds of the spring of childhood and wonderful flowers of the garden of the flower garden of youth, was called «The Wonders of childhood». The second sofa, decorated with rare events in the steppe and the field, youth and passion, adolescence and love, was named «The Rarities of youth». The third sofa, which describes the state of exquisite pleasures from a glass of love and passion

in a tavern of the middle period of life, was called «Middle-aged Curiosities». And the fourth sofa, in which such torments and results of love and passion that appear at the end of life as painful sighs and last gasps are recorded, has acquired the name «Useful tips of old age». And if you define the period from forty-five to about sixty – this is the time of winter, when a person with a bent back enters the path of non-existence and says goodbye to his contemporaries, in prayer for him I brought to the end “Useful tips of old age». All sofas of Alisher Navai, without exception, both during life and after death, enjoyed great national love. They were repeatedly copied by the best calligraphers of that time, and Navai’s poetic fame spread far beyond Khorasan. Largely due to this, today many of the largest libraries in Europe, Asia and America have manuscripts of various books by Alisher Navai, and first of all his sofas. Alisher Navai called his famous sofa «The Treasury of Thoughts». This is absolutely true, since many serious philosophical, socio-political, moral and ethical problems have found their illumination in the poet’s traditional lyrical poetry. The leading theme of Navai’s lyrics was love in a variety of manifestations. In lyrical poems, as in other works of the poet, we find the ideas of a great, exciting love, full of self-denial and self-sacrifice, ideal, pure love. This is, first of all, love for a woman, but not only. This is also love for close people, love for the Motherland, for people in general, because a person is the pearl of life. But only noble, morally pure people are capable of great true love. As you know, Navai was a Sufi. Sufism is a separate extensive topic that requires special consideration, which will definitely be done soon. As a phenomenon, Sufism is much older than Islam, but nevertheless, it is in Islam that Sufism has become known to us precisely as Sufism. Despite the strictness and even severity of the laws of historically established Islam, the vicissitudes of the division of Islam into various branches, Sufism has become a kind of form of self-defense of creativity in Islam, it is Sufi culture in general that has shaped Islamic thought. The most famous thinkers, scientists and poets were Sufis, although it is not customary to talk about this in the Islamic world. This is due to the fact that the dogmatic philosophy of Islam was largely alien to the living Language of Life, and Sufis creatively approached and developed Islam on the basis of this Language, not limiting themselves to dogmatics and rituals, which caused the flourishing of many sciences and literature, formed a special culture that educated the people. Sufism expresses the aspirations and views of the poorest part of the people, who usually find themselves beyond the line of prosperity and wealth. Perhaps it is not by chance that the word Sufism itself is interpreted in different ways, sometimes as «purity» («saf»), then as «sophia» («wisdom»), then as «bench» («suffa»). On

the benches at the mosque built by the Prophet Muhammad in Medina, just huddled the poor. It is believed that the ascetics from Kufa, Abu Hashim (died in 767) and Jabir Ibn Khayyam (died in 867), were the first to receive the nickname «Assufi». In the history of Sufism, of course, there were periods of ups and downs, but its influence on the development of the spiritual culture of the East is decisive and we will analyze this phenomenon of Eastern civilization in future materials. When Alisher Navoi finished his "Five", he wanted to show this work, and had to do it, to his teacher and old friend, Abdurrahman Jami. He took the manuscript, glanced at it— and that was enough: he put his hand on the student's shoulder. And he saw that he was in some wonderful garden, and in this garden there were some majestic men. One of them approached him, it turned out to be Hassan Dehlavi, a famous poet. He told Alisher that these men wanted to talk to him. And now there are three in front of Alisher: Nizami in the middle, Amir Khosrov on the right, and Jami himself on the left. And behind these three stood Firdousi, Unsuri, Nasser Khosrow, Anvari, Khakani, Sanai, Behind. Famous poets from the X-XI centuries. - from the century of Firdousi, to the middle of the XV century. - the century of Jami. Do I need to explain what this meant? Let's not forget who put his hand on the poet's shoulder: his Teacher. Then the Teacher did only what the student only needed: he made the invisible visible, the unconscious-conscious. Jami showed his student to whom "Hamsa" had brought him, into the circle of which people she had introduced him, that is, he showed him both the direction and the meaning of his creative work. And what more can a Teacher do? But the great Teacher did the same for us: we saw what, perhaps, we had not seen so clearly before — these people, these poets belong to one big time, one big epoch, and that this epoch is its own, special. What was that era? To better answer this question, we will add to the names listed some more names of people who also belonged to these five centuries - from XI to XV. These names are: Rudaki, Rumi, Hafiz - great poets; al-Farabi, al-Biruni, Ibn Sina, Ibn Rushd - learned philosophers. Let us also take into account that al-Farabi was then the most authoritative expert on Aristotle, that he combined Aristotelianism with Neoplatonism. Let's not forget that Ibn Sina is none other than Avicenna, that is, the greatest authority in this era and for the West in the science of healing — the science that was the entrance to natural science, at least in that area of it that studies man. Let us remember, finally, that Ibn Rushd is Averroes himself, and averroism was the first hearth in which a spark of rationalistic thought was kindled, the very one that later led to Descartes, Spinoza, Leibniz - great minds who discovered a new structure of

thinking, combined with that complex of new phenomena in the economy, social system, political sphere, which we call the New Time.

The all-consuming power of feeling, high aspirations, deep wisdom imprint the positive heroes of the five great Navoi poems. Developing the centuries-old poetic traditions of the "Five" Nizami, Amir Xycpo and Jami, the poet created a deep original epic cycle, filling traditional plots with a new ideal-artistic service. B poems A. Navoi raises important issues of morality, love and friendship, philosophy, science, art, and the state system for his time. "The Confusion of the Righteous" (1483) is a poem of a philosophical and didactic nature. A large place in it is interested in political issues. The poet sharply criticizes unfair and cruel owners. His ideal is a kind of variant of an enlightened monarchy in an oriental way, the head of which surrounds himself with wise, educated and disinterested advisers. The treachery and greed of the modern poet of the dignitaries and rulers of Navoi are contrasted with the high moral ideals of generosity, generosity, kindness, loyalty in friendship and love, modesty and honesty. Navoi's poem is a hymn to the "bright sky of knowledge", opposed to the "darkness of the night of ignorance". Navoi, admiring the ascetics of science, celebrates people who are real, energetic, striving for a clear, generally useful Goal, and not students of jailers. Humanistic tendencies are visible in the poet's thoughts about the equality of all in the face of fate. The poet praises life, spring, blessed nature, in which solitude is the key to human happiness. Navoi is a thinker and thinker of the epoch of the rise of the culture of Central Asia. The poem "Confusion of the Righteous" is imbued with the humane idea of justice, faith in the triumph of good. These humane ideas are in tune with the Renaissance ideas of the 3rd decade. The poem "Leyli and Majnun" (1484) is a book about the obsession of love, it is not for nothing that the hero of the production-an Arab youth, Kaysa calls "Majnun", i.e. "obsessed with gins". They laugh at him, they put him on a chain, they send him to Mecca, he is forced to run and hide, there is nothing that can temper his love for Leyli.

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